

ABSTRACT

Objective: To evaluate short- and long-term outcomes of elderly patients (≥ 65 years) treated at an intermediate care unit (IMCU) and to identify outcome predictors. Design and setting: Prospective observational study in the IMCU of a university teaching hospital.

Participants: We studied 412 patients over 8 months, classified into three groups: under 65 years (control group, $n = 158$), 65–80 ($n = 186$), and > 80 ($n = 68$).

Measurements: At admission: APACHE II, TISS-28 first day, Charlson Index, diagnosis, and prior Barthel Index. Outcome measures: in-hospital mortality, length of stay, discharge destination, and 2-year mortality and readmissions. Data analysis included multivariate logistic regression and receiver operating characteristics area under the curve (ROC AUC).

Results: No statistically significant differences between groups were observed in hospital mortality (14.1%), discharge to a long-term facility (2.7%), or 2-year readmissions (1.2 ± 2.1). However, hospital stay was longer in patients aged 65–80 years (14 vs. 10 days) and 2-year mortality was higher in those 65 or over (34% vs. 10.6%). In the overall series in-hospital mortality was predicted by APACHE II, first-day TISS-28, and diagnosis (ROC AUC 0.81), and 2-year mortality by Charlson Index and age (ROC AUC 0.77). In the elderly patients 2-year mortality was predicted by Charlson and Barthel indices (ROC AUC 0.70).

Conclusions: Illness severity and therapeutic intervention at admission to IMCU were predictors of short-term mortality, whereas the strongest predictor of long-term mortality was comorbidity. Our results suggest that comprehensive assessment of elderly patients at admission to IMCUs may improve outcome prediction.